

FORMATION OF INNOVATIVE MANAGEMENT COMPETENCIES OF STUDENTS IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITALIZATION OF EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The concepts of "competence" and "managerial competence" are presented in many ways. By competence we mean a short behavioral description of what people do to perform a particular job well or a behavioral standard for effective performance of work. By managerial competence of a specialist we mean a special type of professional competence, representing a set of measurable characteristics of a specialist, which allows him to be effective in his professional activities in the competitive environment of a market economy.*

Keywords: *concepts of "competence" and "managerial competence", high-quality work, standard of effective performance, professional competence, professional activity.*

The concepts of “competence” and “managerial competence” are presented in many different ways. Competence is defined by the National Curriculum as the ability to apply knowledge, skills and personal qualities for successful activity in a certain area. Competence can also be understood as a short behavioral description of what people do to perform a particular job well or a behavioral standard for effective performance of work [2].

Competence, as A.V. Khutorskoy notes in his book, translated from Latin *competentia* means a range of issues in which a person is well informed, has knowledge and experience [5].

A narrower concept is management competence. Having studied a number of studies on this issue, we can understand the management competence of a specialist as a special type of professional competence, representing a set of measurable characteristics of a specialist, which allows him to be effective in professional activities in the conditions of a competitive environment of a market economy. That is, such a personal or business quality, skill, model of behavior, the possession of which helps to successfully solve a certain management task and achieve high results.

It can be noted that there is no consensus on the question of which competencies should be included in the list of managerial competencies of a specialist. The encyclopedia of practical psychology provides the following examples of managerial competencies: the ability to give orders, the ability to resolve conflicts between employees, the willingness to make decisions, focus on results, the ability to work in a team, delegation of authority, and employee motivation.

E.V. Efremenko in her article identifies several groups of qualities of a specialist that make up management skills:

- the ability to communicate on a formal and informal basis and effectively influence colleagues of equal rank;

- the ability to demonstrate the qualities of a leader necessary in communicating with subordinates;

- the ability to navigate in conflict situations and the ability to resolve them;

the ability to receive and process the necessary information, evaluate, compare, and assimilate it;

the ability to make decisions in uncertain situations;

the ability to manage time, distribute work among subordinates, give them the necessary powers, and promptly make organizational decisions;

the ability to demonstrate the business qualities of an entrepreneur: set long-term goals, use favorable opportunities, and change the organizational structure of the enterprise in a timely manner;

the ability to critically evaluate the probable consequences of decisions, and learn from mistakes.

If we return to the concept of "managerial competence", we can say that it is a skill, a model of behavior. Let us also turn to the concept of "function". The Explanatory Dictionary of the Russian Language defines a function as a duty, a range of activities. Thus, to determine the list of management competencies, we will rely on management functions [20].

By planning the author means the definition of the future desired state of the control object, i.e. the goal, and those actions (activities) that must be carried out in order to move from the current state to the desired one. By organization - the placement of elements of the control object, the definition of material and information links between departments, as well as with objects of the external environment.

Control is a comparison of the actual state of the control object with the planned one, identification of discrepancies, their assessment and regulation of the control object in order to eliminate significant discrepancies. Moreover, the author identifies four elements that make up the control function: setting control standards; measuring (accounting) results; comparing the actually achieved results with the established standards; eliminating deviations if necessary.

The last function considered by Komarova is stimulation. Stimulation is understood as rewarding and punishing employees depending on the results of their work activity.

Keith Keenan in the book "Effective Management" also identifies four management functions: planning, organizing, controlling and leading [12].

Goal setting is distinguished as an element of planning. Leadership is understood as instruction, motivation and giving instructions.

G.Ya. Goldstein identifies goal setting as a separate function [6]. Thus, the management ring consists of the following functions: goal setting, planning, organizing, implementing, and controlling.

L.A. Kirzhner and L.P. Kienko note that the functions of managing the company's activities, and accordingly the methods of their implementation, are not immutable; they are constantly modified and deepened. The development and deepening of each management function occurs not only under the influence of internal laws, but also under the influence of the requirements for the development of other functions. Being a common part of the management system, each of the functions must be improved in the direction predetermined by the general goals and objectives of the functioning and development of the company in specific conditions. This leads to a change in the content of each function.

Kirzhner and Kienko in their book "Management of Organizations" provide a classification of management functions according to Fayol, which were formulated back in 1916 [13].

A. Fayol considered management as a sequential series of operations or functions, which are divided into six groups:

- Technical operations - production, manufacturing, processing;
- Commercial operations - purchase, sale, exchange;
- Financial operations - raising capital and managing it;
- Security operations - protection of property and person;
- Accounting operations - balance, costs, statistics;
- Administrative operations - foresight, organization, management, coordination and control.

Administration is only one of the six operations-functions with the help of which management is obliged to ensure the normal course of production. A. Fayol believed that administration occupies a special place in management.

Let's consider the administrative functions in more detail.

Foresight - studying the future, defining a program of action, it covers the previous five operations. A. Fayol here drew attention to the fact that in order to develop an effective program of action, a manager must have: the ability to manage people, activity, moral courage, sufficient fortitude, the necessary competence in this area of activity.

Organization - providing the enterprise with materials, capital, personnel. Here two aspects are distinguished - material and social, i.e. personnel provided with all the necessary material resources must be able to perform the task in social terms. Management - puts the personnel of the enterprise into action after the creation of a social organism. This is the task of management. The goal of management is to obtain the greatest benefit from workers. In all areas of production activity, management is the most important element of work that requires certain qualities.

Control must be effective, i.e. carried out in a timely manner and have practical consequences, but if violations are ignored, such control will be ineffective.

Thus, the five above-mentioned functions were the basis of A. Fayol's administrative doctrine and the basis for all subsequent authors on the problems of the management process.

A.N. Tsvetkov divides all management functions into general (main) and background (auxiliary, connecting) [14].

General functions reflect the technological process (sequence of actions, methods and means of their implementation) of managing a social object.

Tsvetkov attributes the following to the main functions: goal setting, planning, organizing actions, control, and regulation.

Indeed, the sequence of general functions practically reveals the content of the management process.

This process begins with the formation of goals and objectives of the organizations' activities. The formed goals must be achieved. For this, resources, actions, and quantitative characteristics of expected results must be planned, ensuring the achievement of the formed goals, i.e. planning must be performed.

Planned actions must be organizationally supported or organized: organizational structures must be developed, performers must be attracted, their work must be coordinated in time and space, i.e. the organization of the activity must be completed.

After the resources, actions and quantitative characteristics of the expected results have been planned, the necessary actions have been organizationally supported, the process of

implementing the planned and organized activity begins. This process is not performed by the manager, but by his subordinates. But they can understand something or do something incorrectly, therefore, the implementation of activities within the framework of adopted organizational decisions requires control based on the consideration of performance parameters (assessment of the state of work on the implementation of the production program, calendar schedule, expenditure of funds, fulfillment of the staffing schedule, implementation plan, etc.).

As a result of control, deviations from the originally planned course of work are revealed. This means that there is a need to regulate the course of the plan, which consists of developing additional measures aimed at eliminating deviations, or adjusting the formed goals. The regulation function provides feedback in the management process [10].

Background (sometimes called auxiliary) functions or connecting processes are not second-rate in relation to the main ones. They are very important and form the idea of management as a continuous activity, i.e. they create the background for the performance of the main management functions, and are a kind of managerial tools.

Tsvetkov classifies the following as background functions:

- development of solutions;
- establishment of communications;
- motivation of employees.

Sladkevich and Chernyavsky divide management functions into two groups: general and specific.

General (basic) management functions:

- are carried out in each production system and at each management level;
- are inherent in the management of any organization;
- divide the content of management activities into types of work based on the sequence of their implementation in time;
- are relatively independent and at the same time interact.

Among the general functions, the author highlights planning, organization of activities, coordination, regulation, motivation, control, accounting of activities, analysis of activities, decision-making and others.

Specific management functions are the result of management work. Such functions include various types of activities that differ in purpose and method of implementation. Psychological (emotional) qualities are manifested in practice mainly through a person's character. The study of the relationship between such qualities and leadership has led to a fairly long and unlimited list of these qualities. A study of mental (intellectual) qualities showed that the level of these qualities in leaders is higher than in non-leaders. However, subsequent studies have not shown a direct connection between intellectual qualities and leadership. Personal business qualities are largely acquired through experience, in the course of performing their job duties and functions. Their importance for a leader is undoubted, but there is no evidence that their presence ensures the position of an effective leader [12].

Thus, the personal approach to leadership theory suffers from a number of shortcomings and is of little use in practice, but it served as an impetus for the emergence of new approaches to the issue of leadership. After disappointment in the approach to leadership from the position of personal qualities, the attention of scientists was drawn to the behavior of the leader. It was suggested that an effective leader has a set of patterns of habitual behavior in relation to his

subordinates. This version became the basis for the behavioral approach to the study of leadership. This approach became the basis for the emergence of leadership styles, management.

Leadership style reflects:

- the degree to which the manager delegates authority to his subordinates;
- the type of power used;
- methods of working with the external environment;
- ways of influencing personnel;
- the usual manner of behavior of the manager towards subordinates.

The main behavioral models of leadership include the theory "X" and "Y" of D. McGregor, the leadership theory of K. Lewin, the continuum of leadership styles of R. Likert, the management grid (leadership grid) of R. Blake and D. Mouton, the theory of E. Fleischman and E. Harris, etc[21].

The main theories of leadership distinguish two possible behaviors of a leader:

1. behavior focused on human relations (respect for the needs of employees, concern for personnel development);
2. behavior focused on the fulfillment of production tasks at any cost (ignoring the needs and interests of subordinates, underestimating the need for personnel development) [16].

The classification of leadership styles, which is still used today, was proposed by K. Levin. He identified three leadership styles: authoritarian, democratic, liberal. The authoritarian style according to K. Levin assumes the concentration of all power and responsibility in the hands of the leader, the use of threats and psychological influence on subordinates. The liberal style, on the contrary, is the removal of responsibility from the leader, self-distance in favor of the group, providing the team with the opportunity for self-government. The democratic style is a certain optimal combination of the previous two styles and is expressed in the delegation of authority to subordinates with the retention of key positions by the leader [22].

Of interest is the theory of "X" and "Y" by D. McGregor, who was himself an effective leader and enjoyed the respect and trust of his subordinates. He deeply believed that people are naturally proactive, responsible and moral. In support of this, he wrote a book that changed the idea of management theory, which at that time was based on the idea that people are lazy and need to be forced and coerced.

Theory X is based on three basic premises:

1. People don't want to work. People have an innate aversion to work and try to avoid it. Production standards, target performance, and time clocks are management's response to people's natural tendency to shirk.
2. Coercion is inevitable. A company will not achieve its goals without coercing and intimidating its employees. Their only incentive to work is punishment, not reward. Promotions, bonuses, and benefits only increase a person's demands, rather than awakening the desire to work hard.

People try to avoid responsibility. All they want from life is a quiet job with a regular paycheck [11].

Theory "Y" is based on the following postulates:

1. People do not have an innate aversion to work. Under certain conditions, workers enjoy what they do.

2. Employees do not necessarily need to be kept in fear. Properly motivated employees will work without prodding and will make active efforts to solve the problems facing the company.

. The feeling of success gives people pleasure. Achieved success strengthens their self-confidence, and as a result, employees are even more eager to achieve their goals.

People want to do responsible work. It is not true that people are lazy and irresponsible by nature. In fact, on the contrary, they look for any opportunity to do responsible work.

People are naturally creative. Most people are able to creatively solve the problems they face.

People are smart and quick-witted. Often, managers greatly underestimate the intellectual abilities of their subordinates.

Thus, Theory X states that the internal policy of a company should be determined by its management, without consulting the staff. According to Theory Y, management should take into account both the needs of the company as a whole and the needs of its employees, who, in turn, would like to benefit their organization. Employees who know that they can rely on their superiors believe in themselves and are ready to work with high efficiency [17]. Specific functions do not affect the entire production, but rather its specific parts. Each specific function of the organization's management is complex in content and includes general functions.

Let us clarify that by goal setting we mean setting a goal, i.e. defining the future desired state of the studied object (phenomenon). By planning we mean developing actions (events) that must be carried out in order to move from the current state to the desired one. Organization is the distribution of tasks between departments or employees, establishing interaction between them to achieve common goals. Motivation is the process of motivating oneself and other people to act to achieve common goals. Control is a comparison of the actual state of the control object with the planned one, identifying discrepancies, and assessing them. By eliminating deviations, we mean regulating the control object in order to eliminate a significant discrepancy. The last two functions implement feedback. Thus, these functions represent a closed process (management cycle), reflect the types of activities included in the management process, allowing for the effective implementation of management activities, i.e. represent a list of management competencies. To ensure the effectiveness of the process of developing management competencies, it is necessary to comply with a number of organizational and pedagogical conditions.

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